

ISic1360

I.Sicily inscription 1360

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἐνθάδε κῖ
2. τε Κεκιλια
3. νὸς ζήσας
4. ἔτη κ εἰρή
5. νηΙΙ ὑμῖν πᾶ
6. σιν ἐν Θ(ε)ῶ
- 7.

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Here lies Kekilianos, having lived for 20 years. Peace for all of you under god.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492974

EDCS 39101740

PHI 140864

PHI 316259

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